

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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1. Gender equality and gender representation in Spain

1.1. Structural constraints in relation to gender equality

In Spain, since the promulgation of the Spanish Constitution in 1978, equality between women and men has been affirmed in Spain. Almost a decade later, in 1987, the Women's Institute was created to promote and foster the conditions that would enable social equality of both sexes and the participation of women in political, cultural, economic and social life¹.

However, the incorporation of the gender perspective in Spain came about as a result of Organic Law 3/2007 of 22 March 2007, which proposed the prevention of discriminatory behaviour and the provision of active policies to make the principle of equality effective in the different areas of social, cultural and artistic reality in which inequality could be generated and perpetuated, and to make equality between women and men effective². With the implementation of this Organic Law 3/2007, a significant step was taken towards making knowledge of the reality and potential inequalities between men and women more visible, paving the way for the incorporation of the gender perspective in statistics and studies mentioned in Article 20, which states that it must contribute to the recognition and valuation of women's work and avoid the negative stereotyping of certain groups of women. However, although the need to incorporate the gender perspective in statistics and studies is recognised, the truth is that there is very little literature on the subject in Spain, and there is still a long way to go to incorporate the gender perspective in a cross-cutting manner¹. At the autonomous community level, Castilla y León's Statute establishes, in Article 70.1.11, the exclusive competence of the independent community in promoting equal treatment and opportunities between women and men.

Despite the progress that has been seen in the creation of laws and institutions that regulate gender equality, there are still challenges in various work sectors, including equal salaries, equality plans in companies, equality on boards of directors, equality in birth permits³.

¹ Inmujeres, « Origins of the Women's Institute », 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.inmujeres.gob.es/actualidad/noticias/2022/OCTUBRE/indiceuropeoigualdad.htm>.

² BOE, «Ley Orgánica 3/2007, de 22 de marzo, for the effective equality of women and men. », núm. 71, mar. 2007. Retrieved from: <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2007-6115>

³ UOC, «Challenges of gender equality in Spain», 2018. Retrieved from: <https://fp.uoc.fje.edu/blog/retos-de-la-igualdad-de-genero-en-espana/>.

2. Gender representation in History in Spain

2.1. The role of gender representation in crucial areas such as history

Men have always been the protagonists of the different studies in many disciplines, from the great cultural, social, political and economic revolutions, with great invisibility towards the contribution of women in the different disciplines and fields of knowledge; history, literature, philosophy, art, social sciences, engineering, this has consequently resulted in literary, philosophical, artistic, economist and scientific canons being biased in favour of men ⁴.

Woyshner (2002) ⁵ mentions that in many existing curriculum frameworks, women's history content is added to an already full plate. It can be seen as counterproductive, as women are in danger of being lost when attempting to be inclusive within a thematic approach. Women are subsumed under broad themes, but in the process many references to women are omitted so that they appear to be effectively excluded, in any case, women's history remains in a precarious position.

The inclusion of gender diversity is relevant and challenging for schools and teaching. In recent years there has been interest in the presence/absence of women in curricula, syllabi and textbooks, and also in teachers' work on including the invisible in history teaching in particular ⁶. Some authors, such as Scott (2008) ⁷, argue that history has been written to exclude women and gender studies due to patriarchal culture.

Hence the importance of making women visible on an equal footing to men's actions, highlighting repression, marginalisation, absence and gender hierarchies ^{6, 8}. Scott (2008) recognises the importance of rescuing women's actions in constructing historical narratives; however, she argues that reflection should be oriented towards women's empowerment in the face of gender inequalities in history teaching ⁵. Fernández (2006)⁹ agrees that including women could provoke reflection on who have been the protagonists of history. Subirats & Anguita, (2021) ¹⁰ affirm the urgency of building a

⁴ C. García, « Women and history. Questioning invisibility and becoming visible », *Historical processes. Revista de Historia y Ciencias Sociales*, n.º 29, 2016.

⁵ C. Woyshner, «Political History as Women's History: Toward a More Inclusive Curriculum», *Theory & Research in Social Education*, vol. 30, n.º 3, pp. 354-380, jul. 2002, doi: 10.1080/00933104.2002.10473201.

⁶ J. Marolla, « The inclusion of women in history classes: possibilities and limitations from the conceptions of Chilean students », *Rev. Colomb. Educ.*, vol. 1, n.º 77, may 2019, doi: 10.17227/rce.num77-6549.

⁷ J. W. Scott, *Genre and history. Mexico*. Fondo de Cultura Económica, 2008.

⁸ M. Crocco, «Caught between Invisibility and Stereotyping: Teaching the Novel Shabanu», *Social Education*, vol. 70, n.º 4, pp. 178-182, 2006

⁹ A. Fernández, «<< La construcción de identidad desde la perspectiva de Género>>», *Íber*, vol. 47, pp. 33-44.

¹⁰ M. Subirats y R. Anguita, *Educating women: the construction of the coeducational perspective. in equality*, no. n.º 7. Valladolid: Ediciones Universidad de Valladolid, 2021.

teaching that promotes gender diversity and constructing a co-educational perspective. To do so, it is necessary to reinterpret history and establish a space where the role played by women and people who have been silenced by a history that has given prominence to men with power over others is made evident ⁶.

3. Female footprint in Salamanca, Spain

As Pérez-Lucas (1989) ¹¹ mentions, a Salamanca woman is anyone who, whether or not she was born in Salamanca, just because she has spent most of her life there and has played a leading role, has the right to be considered as such.

Salamanca is a city full of stories carried out by women: some focused on power, literature, science, those who fought for the city, those who have given their lives to the spiritual exercise of religious life and popular women such as craftswomen, among many others (Table 1).

Table 1. Female figures in Salamanca

Women	History	Type of conservation	Footprint
Mujeres Vacceas	In 220 B.C., the Vacceas abandoned the passive role assigned to them and proved their courage by taking up the fight and defending their city.	Roman Bridge, Arch of Hannibal and El Verraco.	City Conservation
Doña Urraca y Doña Mafalda	Doña Urraca and her husband were assigned the task of repopulating Salamanca. Furthermore, on her father's death, Alfonso VI, the Kingdom was left in her hands. On her remarriage to "El Batallador", they were proclaimed kings of León and Castile. Mafalda dies in Salamanca and is buried in the Old Cathedral, next to the main altarpiece presided over by the Virgen de la Vega, patron saint of the city.	Avenida de Doña Urraca	
Beatriz Galindo	Latin teacher at Isabela Católica. She created several foundations: The Santa Cruz Hospital, monasteries such as the Franciscan-Conceptionist monasteries and the Conception Hieronymite monastery.	La Latina" Street	A cultured and learned woman from Salamanca for her mastery of grammar and Latin.

¹¹ M. D. Pérez-Lucas, *Singular Women from Salamanca (220 A.C.-Siglo XIX)*. Amaru, 1989.

Feliciana Enríquez de Guzmán	She defied society by dressing as a man in order to study at university. She graduated with a degree in canons, becoming a well-known Spanish poet and playwright.	University of Salamanca	Student who broke the mould imposed by society
Dolores Cebrián Fernández Villegas	Born in Salamanca, and also studied like the men.	University of Salamanca	Student
Santa Teresa de Jesús	Honorary doctorate from the University of Salamanca. The first woman to be awarded a doctorate by the Catholic Church. She wrote prose, poetry and short stories. She had a profound and analytical vision.	Sculpture in the street. Santa Teresa Street Santa Teresa de Jesús House	
Matilde Cherner	She was a writer and journalist. She signed with the masculine name "Rafael de Luna". She was concerned with social issues and the role of women in society.	University of Salamanca	Literature
Carmen Martín Gaité	Philology student, professionally successful, an award-winning writer in the history of Spanish literature.	University of Salamanca	Literature
María del Rosario López Piñuelas	Philosophy and Literature student, with a special talent for theatre.	University of Salamanca	Theatre
Helena Pimenta	She is a Spanish stage director, playwright and theatre director. She studied English and French Philology at the University of Salamanca.	University of Salamanca	Theatre
“La brava”: Doña María Rodríguez de Monroy		Plaza de los Bandos	
Doña Gonzala Santana: “La polilla de Oro”	A woman who, despite being wealthy, chose to remain single, a rare occurrence in her time. She dedicated her life to helping the most needy, donated money to construct a school and created scholarships for the poorest children. She is one of the benefactors of the Vera Cruz brotherhood.	Gonzala Santana Street	
Gobernadoras de Salamanca	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doña Berenguela de Castilla “La grande” • Doña María de Molina • Doña María de Portugal • Juana Manuel • Doña Leonor de Aragón • Doña María de Aragón 	Plaza Mayor	Women in politics
Las Freiras Comendadoras de Sacti-Spiritus	Women of the nobility. They fought to defend their privileges against the Grand Master of Santiago.	Comendadoras Street	Women of Faith

Las Emparedadas	The Emparedadas, women locked in cells in the walls of the churches, although it is said that they were dedicated to visiting the sick, making clothes and liturgical clothes for the offices.	San Esteban Church, Sancti-Spíritus Church, Santa María, San Sebastián and San Juan de Bábalos Church	Women of Faith
La Negrita	A woman famous for having the gift of prophecy and for performing miracles.	Convento de la Penitencia	Women of Faith
Romana “La Merenguera”	A woman who filled the lives of the people of Salamanca with joy, representing the craftswomen who were great entrepreneurs in the city.	Plaza Mayor	Popular characters
Teresa Vicente Mosquet			
María de Maeztu	She was one of the first women officially enrolled as a student at the University of Salamanca. She was a disciple of Miguel de Unamuno. She is linked to the promotion of equality through education and to the commitment to a fairer and more caring society through a life dedicated almost entirely to the fight against illiteracy, to the universalisation of reading, to the education of women, to the establishment of coeducation for girls and boys, to the reinforcement of humanistic values in the classroom.		
Lucía de Medrano	The story of Lucía de Medrano reflects the intellectual atmosphere of the time: the liberal and humanist thought of the University. In the midst of the shadows of the Middle Ages, the lights of Humanism gradually appeared, demanding a change in the role of women in society and the characters of women like Lucía de Medrano at the University of Salamanca.		
María Telo Núñez	The woman who achieved, still under Franco's regime, the reform of the Civil Code in 1975 by which the so-called "Marital Licence" and "Obedience" to the husband were abolished.		
Ana Díaz Medina	Dr. Ana Díaz Medina was a Professor of History at the University of Salamanca. For more than four decades and until her		

	retirement, she developed a valuable teaching and research activity at the University of Salamanca. Since 2002, she has been director of the Centre for Women's Studies at the University of Salamanca (CEMUSA). From the Centre she promoted numerous activities and initiatives. One of these initiatives was the CEMUSA journal: Estudios multidisciplinares de género.		
Magdalenas Garretas Sastre	Degree in Philosophy and Letters in 1934. Graduated with Extraordinary Prize. Assistant to Unamuno, she later became a Greek Language and Literature lecturer. She became a secondary school teacher and taught until her retirement in 1982.		

4. Local strategies

Regarding local strategies for the promotion of women's history, the Municipal Institute of Education of Salamanca City Council has created a support booklet to learn about the history of the Women of Salamanca and a map of routes where these women are located, whether in streets, monuments or squares.

In addition, the Salamanca City Council has implemented different workshops for the promotion of Women in the History of Salamanca, highlighting content such as Vaccean women among invading armies, Women among Monarchs: Queens, consorts, princesses and lovers, University Women: Beatriz de Galindo, Lucía de Medrano, Teresa de Jesús, Dolores Cebrián, Feliciano Enríquez, Carmen Martín Gaité, Matilde Cherner and Women in the medallions of the Plaza de Salamanca.

The Salamanca City Council, in collaboration with Turismo de Salamanca, is organising a series of guided tours throughout May. These are free visits to highlight the relevant role of some of the women in the history and heritage of the city, which they call "Salamanca with a woman's voice", this visit is carried out in order to give visibility to the relevant women in the history of Salamanca, from the Casa de la Mujer Clara Campoamor and its School of Equality.

The Salamanca City Council's website also provides accessible information about important figures in the city, such as Saint Teresa of Jesus (<https://salamanca.es/es/productos-turisticos/huellas-de-teresa>). The organisation organises competitions to make women more visible, such as the "For Equality" Graffiti

and

Mural

Painting

Competition

(<http://www.familiaeigualdad.aytosalamanca.es/es/mujer/concursosycertamenes/concursos/Graffitis.html>).

On the other hand, the opening of the Casa de la Mujer "Clara Campoamor" by the City Council shows its priority in the fight for equality and the rights of all women.

Likewise, different routes can be found in the Salamanca Tourist Office, including the Huella de Santa Teresa, a woman who has contributed to the history of Salamanca, with her enterprising spirit, literary quality, spirituality and reformist values.

In Salamanca, several exhibitions have been held, such as the one exhibited in the Torrente Ballester Municipal Library on 10 and 29 May 2020 called "Women who change history" by the artist Pilar Vega Pérez, by means of a collage with the faces of 37 women fighters, artists, vindicators, avant-garde, pioneers and forgotten women.

Likewise, the University of Salamanca, the City Council, the Junta de Castilla y León and the associations ID arte and Mujeres dos Rombos presented the project "Rostros del Olvido", a project that makes visible those women who studied at the University of Salamanca throughout its history and did important work, but were unjustly left in the shadows.

At the level of the community of Castilla y León, there are various associations that, in the common interest of women, organise themselves to make the work of women in the community visible, such as the association APFCyL, which is in charge of making women visible in the media of Castilla y León.

5. Focus Groups with Young People: Analyses and results

5.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

There has been very little training in history, it has been the interviewees' own interest that has led them to investigate more about history and find certain information that interested them, this helped to generate interest in other areas and themes of history. The participants consider that history is not focused on in any sense, it is given in a very isolated way, and it is not fully integrated in the contents of education, but they are interested in history because, as they say, if you don't study it you are condemned to repeat it. One of the things that is repeated the most is that it does not focus on current history, and that it does not manage to give all the complete content, they only focus on some events that they consider more relevant, leaving out most of the events, and when it comes to the role of women in history, it is not even mentioned. Of all the young participants, only one person had attended a camp, and even in this camp it was mainly about historical figures, mainly men.

5.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

The participants have made it clear that the way history is taught is very poorly thought out, moreover, the teaching is always biased by the person who tells it, the knowledge that is transmitted is done in a fragmented way, only focusing on students memorising dates without any common thread, leaving aside the whole historical process, moreover, the subject of history is given in a fragmented way or by blocks and recent history is not studied. As the participants commented, perhaps it would be better to try to teach it as a process and not as an event in parcels, because in the process perhaps the name of a woman appears. In the end, history is something that is alive and cannot be studied in such a static and linear way. The methodology must be changed. They also see a lack of representation of women in textbooks and several anonymous ones, women are always invisible. The way history is taught must change so that it is not just about fulfilling the curriculum; teachers must be more involved.

5.3. Female figures and male figures

The participants commented that their balance is very unbalanced, and that the names that came to mind were mostly men's names and this is due to the fact that this name is always repeated constantly, contrary to what happens with women's names that are omitted or not even pronounced and remain in oblivion. For some participants it was easier to remember some iconic names of women in contemporary literature, philosophers. Men's names: Dalí, Picasso, Da Vinci. Women's names: Rosa Cobo, María Zambrano, Isabela Católica, María Montessori, Simone de Beauvoir, Virginia Woolf, Clara Campoamor, Aleksandra Kolontái, Amelia Valcárcel, Andrea Durkin.

5.4. Importance of gender representation

It is very important to consider the representation of all genders, women, non-binary people, and other communities, not just men. Making women's achievements visible can serve as an inspiration to young women who identify with them. Represent the full spectrum of people who contribute to and produce for history and progress to fill the gap in all fields, representing figures from the past and present in all disciplines.

5.5. Gender misrepresentation

The participants consider that the erroneous representation of gender comes from the structure of the system, from the role that has been established for women as reproducers and not producers. In the end, women have always been on the margins, reduced to the private sphere, and social pressure has conditioned women's reality,

making their work and achievements invisible. In addition, the gender roles or stereotypes that are adopted are conditioned by society and this leads to invisibilisation.

5.6. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'.

A change in methodology is important, debate and critical thinking must be promoted among students, women in history must be integrated into the curriculum, and content must be updated. There must be a change in education. The curriculum must be balanced in terms of what is taught about men and women. It cannot be that the section that talks about women is on the last page, isolated, as if it were worthless.

Women can be made visible through photographic exhibitions.

- Art, oriented towards music, theatre, building things with the hands, in individual or group work.
- Creation of audiovisual content
- Encourage students by giving them extra points in the final assessment if they watch historical series or films and discuss them in class.
- Micro-dramas can be made, with certain historical sequences.
- Change the content or the curriculum, so that it is not always the teacher who gives the class, but the student who takes an active role in the class,
- Offer more dynamic classes,
- Encourage dynamic workshops, shock therapies,
- Role-playing games.

5.6.1 Collaborations

It would be interesting to do:

- Collaborations with the University of Salamanca and the UPSA, regarding the visibility of female characters.
- Collaborations with tourist guides.
- Collaboration with those who are dedicated to making micro-theatres in certain tourist areas and to make the role of women visible.
- Collaboration with public figures, influencers, etc.
- Tour the city and ask people questions about certain important female figures in the city.

5.6.2 Transnational map

- Add a suggestion section where you can propose a female name that has contributed to the city.
- It should be an interactive, live, dynamic map, allowing links to videos, a documentary or interactive images and, if a Twitch or TikTok channel is created, to be able to link to it. Not just mentioning dates or a timeline.
- Imagine a map full of pins, with varied information, where you can discover new characters from various fields, and not just focus on 4 of the most emblematic names.

- In addition, it would be interesting if it were very visual, with audio resources.

A map classified by areas of history, disciplines, territories that is layered, that is not told in a linear way.

5.6.3 Digital tools

- Social Media, create an Instagram account where you collect profiles of women throughout history, you can create smaller videos with concise information, also allow comments where other people provide more information.
- Tiktok.
- Twitch channel.
- Video games.
- Create a YouTube channel.
- Short and entertaining sketches.
- Creating 5 minute pills, playing with clickbait unknowns.
- Create a podcast where you can interview different women in current history.

6. Focus Groups with Stakeholders: Analyses and results

6.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

Some Stakeholders mention that the link with history has been little, and that perhaps very little is dedicated to seeing what is current and focuses a lot on the old, so it is difficult to rescue what has not been made known or made visible at the time, however, it has been in their work where they have become aware of the importance of making women visible, such as women in STEM, or the visibility of women researchers in history, technologists, also working with other communities such as people with disabilities or LGTB+ people. We know a little about history and what was given to them and what they were interested in for their own interest or particular character at some point, but very little about the history of women. Moreover, history has always been told from the male perspective. The invisibility of women is almost complete. There is a very long history of women. The main and most active participation is on 11 February (International Day of Women and Girls in Science) through different associations across Europe, such as the Association of Women in Research and Technology in Spain (AMIT) and other members of the European Platform of Women Scientists, where women in research are made visible.

6.2. Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise' : Challenges or difficulties

Some stakeholders consider that their lack of time or inexperience limits them in the transmission of content, leaving aside topics such as gender perspective or history. They often focus on current affairs, because young people are losing interest, and they see

current content or more contemporary characters as more relatable and identifiable. Another big challenge is the content of textbooks, which contain very few female figures. Another challenge is the bias in the interpretation and language used, as well as the loss of identity. It must be institutionalised and not just a matter of voluntarism. It must be integrated into the curriculum and taught as a matter of course.

6.3. Findings on ‘Experience with young people in the field of History’

It is complicated to see the interest of children and young people. It is not that they are not interested in the history of women in Salamanca (Spain), it is just the way it is presented to them, the same happens with other subjects such as mathematics, language. There is little interest, but not much less than in other subjects. Incorporating gender issues in the classroom is important, even if it is met with a certain amount of boredom on the part of the young people, resistance that is difficult to overcome. The lack of interest on the part of young people is related to the fact that the education system does not provide them with information related to women. The role of making teachers visible is important, having the interest to provide this content. There are young people who already have some previous interest, who are proactive and when they are given more information, their interest is awakened.

6.4. Findings on ‘Women’s footprint in History’

6.4.1 Methods of transmission

- Practical, tangible things so that it is internalised, manageable and interactive. It is very important how it is told.
- In libraries, narratives can be created from images, references in works of literature.
- Implement active methodologies.
- Gamification.
- Project work.
- Inverted classes.
- Launch a competition in schools. Let them make videos, comics, audios .
- Introduce the intersectional perspective.
- The importance of women in all public spaces must be communicated and publicised at an early stage.

6.4.2 Representation

Male characters are well represented, the focus should be on women only. It is always necessary to disseminate for men and women and not to segregate men and boys. The diversity of scientific and historical knowledge should be presented. Represent women careers, women who have done social work in the history of Salamanca. Recover the

memory of women in the different disciplines. When it comes to recovering the memory, the intersectional perspective must be introduced, as the memory of university women, literate women, high and low social classes, etc. must be recovered.

6.4.3 Transnational Map

- An interactive map.
- Introduce gamification, perhaps make it like a geocaching map.
- Use more graphic things, such as introducing the information of the woman in a monument and by passing the mobile phone over it, it gives you all the information.
- A map with simple information, simple, short, like an infographic, very visual and complement it with small videos.
- Focus not only on historical places but also outside the city.

6.4.4 Collaborations

- Connect with public libraries, implement activities in them.
- Connect with associations that offer activities, complementary workshops such as the Ciudad de los Niños programme and youth centres.
- Collaboration with influencers, public figures, ambassadors who talk about women's legacies in history.
- Sightseeing tours.
- It is important not only to recover the memory of women, but also spaces and meeting places.

6.4.5 Digital Tools

- Tiktok.
- Memes.
- Using artificial intelligence to tell a message, give women a voice and let them tell their story.
- Video games.
- Social networks: Instagram, Facebook.
- Mobile App.

6.4.6 Suggestions from participants on female footprint in the city/in history

- Teresa Vicente Mosquete. Dept. Geography. She wrote a book: Streets with a woman's name: Women in the streets. A history to be written on the walls of our cities - *Calles con nombre de mujer: La mujer en el callejero. Una historia por escribir en los muros de nuestras ciudades*, in *La historia no contada: Mujeres pioneras 2007*.
- María Telo Nuñez was the protagonist of the reforms of the Civil Code in 1975 and 1981, the third woman to be awarded Honoris Causa in the history of the University of Salamanca.
- Lucía de Medrano, María Maeztu linked to the University of Salamanca.
- Magdalena Garretas, who was Unamuno's assistant.
- Ana Díaz Medina. She was the first director of the Seminary, a specialist in modern history. She was the first to implement a subject on the history of

modern women in the Faculty of History, and from then on, the following courses were developed.

7. Conclusions

Despite the significant progress made with the incorporation of gender perspectives in Spain, driven by the implementation of laws and the establishment of institutions promoting gender equality, there are still various challenges to face. Therefore, it is essential to advocate for the equal visibility of women in all sectors of society, aiming to eradicate gender-based repression, marginalization, absence, and hierarchies.

In Salamanca, specifically, different initiatives have been undertaken to promote women's history, both within educational centers and by the local government, through activities such as workshops and exhibitions. While the number of visible women in Salamanca is proportionally smaller compared to men, some of their names can be found on the most representative streets and squares in the city.

On the other hand, focus groups with young people and stakeholders have emphasized the importance of implementing initiatives to showcase women's history in Salamanca in a dynamic and interactive manner. They recommend leveraging digital resources to reach more young individuals and spark their interest in learning about these topics. By doing so, we can progress towards a more inclusive society that recognizes and appreciates the vital role of women in history and in the present.